

COMBINED USE OF ORGANOSOLV LIGNIN AND XANTHATES ON SPHALERITE FLOTATION FROM MIXED SULPHIDES

P. M. Angelopoulos[#], G. Anastassakis, N. Kountouris, N. Koukoulis,
M. Taxiarchou

National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), School of Mining and
Metallurgical Engineering, Greece

ABSTRACT – The use of xanthates at the flotation of sphalerite raises questions about the sustainability of the process, due to the negative environmental impact. In addition, the development of local bio-collectors production is necessary to replace currently utilized flotation collectors and depressants, which are manufactured mostly in China. In this study we investigate the performance of lignin nanoparticles as sphalerite collectors in combination with xanthates. Among the parameters tested are replacement ratio, dilution temperature and lignin type. Interestingly, the partial replacement of xanthate collectors with bio collector lignin is viable. We tested a variety of attributes such as concentration, lignin types and sizes with a 3-stage flotation. After evaluation of the products is showed that a 50% replacement of collector with lignin does not affect the sphalerite grades and recovery, while decreasing the recovery of the gangue mineral (Au), thus leading to improved selectivity.

Keywords: Sphalerite, Flotation, Lignin, Collector, Selectivity.

INTRODUCTION

Froth flotation is the most widely applied technique for the recovery of sphalerite from mixed sulfides. Sphalerite's floatability is greatly enhanced by the exchange of Zn ions with metal ions of the pulp, acting as active sites to react with collector. Long-chain xanthate works effectively as a collector in sphalerite flotation [1]. The use of xanthates however possesses certain important drawbacks related to the followings; (i) serious environmental impact, (ii) the centralized production that is mainly in China, and (iii) the quality variation that affect the flotation performance.

Lignin nanoparticles and microparticles are sustainable and environmental friendly materials, possessing satisfactory performance in Cu flotation [2]. In this paper, we investigate the potentiality of the use of lignin as collector in sphalerite flotation. More specifically, we tested the use of lignin micro- and nanoparticles from different origins, in different proportions for the selective recovery of sphalerite, and evaluated the results in terms of zinc and gangue minerals grade and recovery.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Lignin preparation

Birch and spruce wood chips were pretreated with organosolv to remove the lignin,

[#] corresponding author: pangelopoulos@metal.ntua.gr

which was then utilized to create lignin nanoparticles [3]. The spruce woodchips were pretreated in a 60% v/v ethanol in water solution at 183 °C for 1 hour whereas the birch woodchips were pretreated at 183 °C in a 50% v/v ethanol in water solution. The ethanol/water solution's 5% w/v lignin was then homogenized at 750 bars using a pressure homogenizer. Deionized water was used to further dilute the homogenized liquid, which caused nanoparticles to develop. The material was freeze dried in order to produce nanoparticles as a dry powder.

Chemical and mineralogical analyses

In this study, a mixed sulphide ore containing Pyrite, Arsenopyrite, Galena, Sphalerite from Olympiada, Chalkidiki was obtained from the production line of HellasGold facility. The sample was obtained from the tailing of galena recovery circuit thus possessing minimum lead content. The ore d_{80} was 130 μm . **Table 1** presents the chemical analysis expressed in oxides. ZnO content is about 4.33%. In addition, as it is known that gold particles are distributed inside pyrite and arsenopyrite ores, and it is important to avoid its collection[3]. Moreover, the Loss On Ignition (LOI) of the sample was found to be relatively high at 12.86%, attributed to the decomposition of various sulphide minerals.

Table 1 Total Oxide X-Ray Analysis with X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometer for ZnS feed

Element	Content (%)
PbO	0.69
ZnO	4.33
Fe ₂ O ₃	17.81
As ₂ O ₃	5.25
S	12.12
Sb	0.03
CuO	0.04
C	3.42
MgO	1.73
Al ₂ O ₃	4.67
SiO ₂	18.80
K ₂ O	0.97
CaO	13.83
MnO	0.98
Loss On Ignition	12.86
Other	2.46

A modal analysis was done by chemically balancing the elements to their corresponding minerals and presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Modal analysis of ZnS feed

Ore	Content (%)
Galena (PbS)	0.74
Sphalerite (ZnS)	5.18
Pyrite (FeS)	14.09
Arsenopyrite (FeAsS)	6.04

Experimental procedure

Seven different flotation experiments were carried out with a constant solid ratio of ~45% and stirring speed of 1500 rpm. The flotation experiments were divided into 2 main categories; on the first, the gradual replacement of xanthate by lignin was implemented, and on the second, 4 different types of lignin were utilized. **Table 3** shows the quantity of reagents, as well as the conditioning and frothing times and the pH.

Table 3 Flotation reagents dosages, pH and duration

Stages	pH	Conditioning (min)	Frothing (min)	CuSO4 (g/t)	SIPX/Lignin (g/t)
Conditioning	10	5		270	48
Rougher	9.5-10		2		
Scavenger 1	9.5-10	1	2		12
Scavenger 2	9.5-10		1		

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 presents Zn and Au grade and recovery in the concentrate, in terms of the xanthate replacement ratio. The 50% replacement of SIPX by lignin allowed the production of concentrate with similar properties of the one obtained using solely SIPX, in terms of Zn grade and recovery. Also, the addition of lignin in collector mixture increases selectivity, through decreasing of the Au grade and recovery. The use of chemical collector SIPX recovered 85% of the sphalerite inside the ore but also 45% of the gangue mineral (Au). By adding 50% SIPX and 50% lignin as collectors, an increase in selectivity is evident by reducing the recovery of gold by 33% (from 45.9% to 30.5%), in comparison with the SIPX collector, while maintaining the same Zn recovery. On the contrary, for 100% replacement of chemical collector, Zn recovery decreases significantly making it apparent that a full replacement of chemical collector is not possible. By using only lignin as a collector, a Zn recovery of 54% is possible.

Figure 1 Chemical collector replacement with lignin

The selectivity index was developed by Gaudin as the practical approach to measure two-way separation [4].

$$SI = \sqrt{\frac{Rv \times Rg}{(100 - Rv) \times (100 - Rg)}} \quad (1)$$

where R_v % is the recovery of Zn in the flotation concentrate, and R_g % is the recovery of gangue (Au) in the tailing fraction. By definition, the selectivity index (SI) can be used to show the degree to which valuable minerals are separated from the gangue ones. The SI takes into account two parameters: the recovery of precious minerals in the concentrate and the recovery of gangue minerals in the tailing. Another, criterion for evaluating the results is the separation efficiency [5], which is use for evaluating the separation of the mineral, focusing on the recovery of valuable and gangue minerals in the concentrate. SE is given by the following equation:

$$SE = R_a - R_b \quad (2)$$

where R_a and R_b are the recoveries of valuable and gangue minerals in the concentrate respectively. **Table 4** presents SE and SI, together with Zn and Au recovery, in terms of the SIPX replacement ratio by lignin. As it shown, the SI of Control sample is 2.6 and the separation efficiency is 38.9. By 100% replacement with lignin, the SI increases to 3.5 and also the SE increases to 44.8, but with very low recovery grades as mentioned earlier. Though, the maximum SE value was obtained applying a 50%/50% SIPX/lignin collector mixture; the SE increased from 38.9 (control sample) to 53.3, a solid 27% increase, and at the same time the selectivity from 2.6 to 3.4.

Table 4 Selectivity Index and separation efficiency parameters

Collector 60 (g/t)	Zn recovery in concentrate, R_{vZn} (%)	Au recovery in tailing, R_{gAu} (%)	Au recovery in concentrate, R_{bAu} (%)	Separation Efficiency, SE	Selectivity Index, SI
SIPX 100 %	84.8	54.1	45.9	38.9	2.6
SIPX/BN 50/50 %	83.8	69.5	30.5	53.3	3.4
SIPX/BN 50/100 %	80	67.4	32.6	47.4	2.9
BN 100%	53.7	91.1	8.9	44.8	3.5

At last, a comparison between 4 different types of lignin was investigated regarding their particle sizes (μm and nm) and qualities (Birch and Spruce). The results are presented in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 Lignin type replacement graph

Overall, no considerable difference in flotation performance is observed among the different types. The grades of sphalerite derived range between 14.8 - 17% and the recoveries between 27.3-37.1%, which are very low. A difference at the final recoveries of Zn with Spruce Micro as a collector is identified, however, it is not considered remarkable, in combination with the overall low recovery achieved.

CONCLUSIONS

Lignin micro- and nanoparticles have been as collectors in copper bearing minerals flotation with satisfactory results. Lignin is ecofriendly and produced from a practically abundant raw material. In this study we investigate the potentiality of the partial replacement of xanthates by lignin in the flotation of sphalerite from mixed sulfides. The effect of different SIPX/lignin collectors' proportions was investigated in terms of the Zn and Au grade and recovery in the concentrate.

At the control sample a 60 g/t SIPX was used as a collector, achieving Zn recovery and grade of 85% and 12%, respectively. Since Au is solely found in arsenopyrite and pyrite minerals, and knowing that both minerals should be depressed and recovered in a later flotation circuit, Au was also measured targeting minimum recovery at the existing concentrate and considered as a gangue. In the concentrate produced using SIPX, the Au recovery and grade was 45.9 % and 13.4%, respectively. With the use of 50/50% lignin/SIPX collectors' mixture, Zn grade increased to 13.5%, without changing recovery. A sharp decrease of Au recovery in concentrate was observed from 45.9% to 30.5%, possessing beneficial impact to the process eliminating the gold bearing minerals losses. When using the 100% SIPX solution the SI was 2.6, and increased to 3.4 in case of using the 50/50% lignin/SIPX collectors' mixture. The same trend is observed for the concentrate separation efficiency, which for sole SIPX usage it was 38.9 and with the lignin addition increased to 53.3, a 27% performance increase. No significant differences in flotation performance were observed among different lignin grades (micro and nano sized, originated from spruce and birch). The obtained results show that a partial replacement of toxic xanthate by eco-friendly lignin as sphalerite collector is viable, possessing better selectivity, and improving the environmental footprint of the process.

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